

MULTI-SCALE MODELING OF THERMO-OXIDATIVE DEGRADATION IN HIGH TEMPERATURE POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES FOR ADVANCED AIRCRAFT

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SUMMARY

Mechanism-based modeling of damage evolution in high temperature polymer matrix composites (HTPMC) under thermo-oxidative aging conditions is presented in this paper. Specifically, a multi-scale model based on micro-mechanics analysis in conjunction with continuum damage mechanics is developed to simulate the accelerated fiber-matrix debond growth in the longitudinal direction of a unidirectional HTPMC. Benchmark of model prediction with experimental observations of oxidation layer growth is presented, together with a laminate thermo-oxidative life prediction model based on continuum damage mechanics to demonstrate proof-of-concept.

Keywords: Micromechanics, Darcy's Law, Diffusion, Continuum Damage Mechanics , Debond

INTRODUCTION

In order to support materials selection for the next-generation supersonic transport aircraft, a study has been undertaken to evaluate the material constitutive relationships needed to describe advanced polymer matrix composites under conditions of high load and elevated temperature. The primary challenge to the use of HTPMC is due to hygro-thermal effects at temperature (100-300⁰C) resulting in thermo-oxidative degradation and accelerated damage evolution. Various researchers have studied the thermo-oxidative aging process by developing model based design and novel-material systems that enhance the life and affordability of HTPMC. Colin et al. [1] developed a kinetic model to predict the depth of the oxidized layer for a F655-2 bismaleimide polymer resin. The model is based on a differential equation analogous to Fick's law in which the oxygen diffusion and its consumption rate $r(C)$ are coupled, where C is the oxygen concentration. Their model predictions were in excellent agreement with experimental results. More recently, Colin et al. [2] enhanced their kinetic model to predict relative mass loss in a T800H/BMI composite by assuming that the volatile formation results essentially from hydroperoxide

decomposition. The enhanced model was also able to take into account the fact that mass loss is reduced due to the stabilizing effect of carbon fibers due to the scavenging of the peroxy radicals by carbon. Again, excellent agreement with experimental gravimetric results was observed. Tandon et al. [3, 4] extended the kinetic model by introducing the concept of polymer availability state variable, thereby producing predictive oxidative layer growth simulations for a high temperature polyimide, PMR-15. Macroscopic weight loss measurements were used to determine the reaction and polymer consumption parameters. A parametric sensitivity analysis was used to determine the sensitivity of the controlling parameters. It was observed that the oxidation growth process was diffusion controlled, and that the diffusivity of the oxidized zone is the controlling parameter. Recently, Pochiraju et al. [5] have studied the thermo-oxidative behaviour of unidirectional composite material. Their work deals with thermo-oxidative layer growth and damage growth with time. The modulus of PMR-15 is sensitive to the temperature and oxidation state. Due to strong anisotropy in thermo-oxidative response of G30-500/PMR-15 composite, accelerated oxide layer growth is observed in the fiber direction as compared with the direction transverse to the fibers. They have demonstrated the effect of fiber fraction on diffusivity and the effect of a diffusive interface at the lamina scale. It is also observed that compressive modulus of PMR-15 resin decreases from 4.72 to 3.39 GPa due to temperature rise from 25°C to 288 °C as obtained from nano-indentation data of un-oxidized resin. Wang et al [6] have developed a computational micromechanics approach, based on a recently developed coupled constitutive theory with reaction and micro-structural damage for polymer-matrix composites in a high-temperature environment. Micromechanics formulation of the problem is derived to include coupled anisotropic thermal oxidation reaction, mass transport, and thermo-mechanical damage in the fiber composites. Talreja [7] has developed constitutive stress-strain relationships for basic configurations containing distributed damage entities. In this model a continuum concept is used which considers composites as homogeneous anisotropic bodies with distributed damage as the internal structure. It uses the basic laws of thermodynamics and damage tensor as internal variables in the functional relationships of response functions. Recently, Talreja [8] discussed multi-scale modeling aspects of damage and operating mechanisms in unidirectional ceramic matrix composites and cross-ply polymer matrix composite laminates.

COHESIVE LAYER MODELING OF ANISOTROPY IN THERMO-OXIDATIVE DEGRADATION

It has been observed in surface weight-loss rate experiments performed on unidirectional G30-500/PMR-15 polymer matrix composite laminate aged at 288°C at Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL), that oxygen diffusion, and consequently, polymer weight loss exhibits anisotropic behavior. The weight loss in the direction transverse to the fibers is actually lower than the weight-loss for neat resin samples due to the retarding effect of the carbon fibers on oxygen diffusion, as predicated by the rule-of-mixtures. However, the weight loss in the longitudinal (fiber) direction is observed to be greatly accelerated due to synergistic interactions between the fiber, matrix, and the interface. It is conjectured that polymer shrinkage due to thermal oxidation may be responsible for debond initiation and propagation along fiber-matrix interfaces, thereby allowing accelerated penetration of

Figure 1. Micrograph of fiber/matrix debond due to thermo-oxidation in G30-500/PMR-15 composite at 288 °C in air. [10]

Figure 2. Normalized cubic traction-separation law for cohesive layer

oxygen into the laminate, followed by thermal oxidation. A micrograph showing evidence of fiber/matrix debond due to thermo-oxidative resin shrinkage is presented in Figure 1. Modified Fick's Law for diffusion reaction with orthotropic diffusivity is used for modeling [9]. In order to simulate thermo-oxidative resin shrinkage, a cohesive layer model was introduced at the interface of the polymer and fiber within the framework of a finite element analysis of a representative volume element (RVE) using an in-house test-bed code (NOVA-3D, [10, 11]). Based on a cohesive zone model proposed by Needleman [12], a cubic traction-separation law is employed to simulate the material behavior at the fiber/matrix interface, as shown in Figure 2. In the present model, the cohesive layer is assumed to have a finite thickness, approximately equal to the thickness of the sizing at the fiber/matrix interface. It is important to note that the elastic modulus of polymer matrix varies with ageing time and polymer state variable ϕ as suggested by Wise [13],

$$E(\phi, T, t) = E_{un}(T) \exp(K_{ox} \frac{1-\phi}{1-\phi_{ox}}) \exp(K_{nox} \frac{1-\phi}{1-\phi_{ox}} t) \quad (1)$$

where $K_{nox}=0$ and $K_{ox}=0.1878$ for PMR-15, T is temperature, and t is time. Further, it is notable that significant polymer shrinkage strains - on the order of 30 to 40 % at elevated temperatures were observed by researchers at the Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL, Dayton, Ohio).

ANALYTICAL MODEL TO PREDICT DEBOND LENGTH USING DARCY'S LAW FOR OXYGEN DIFFUSION

Assuming that the fiber/matrix debond is initiated and propagated by the shrinkage strain in the surrounding polymer matrix due to oxidative degradation, it is proposed that the debond fracture surface is not smooth, but that it exhibits significant roughness due to the presence

Figure 3. Debonding due to oxygen permeation/diffusion at the fiber/matrix interface

Figure 4. Least squares curve fit for debond length vs. time, of the form $B\sqrt{t}$

of oxidation products as well as fractured polymer fibrils along the interface. Consequently, the flow of oxygen to the debond tip may be represented as one-dimensional axisymmetric flow through a porous media, as depicted in Figure 3, where d is the debond length, and x_0 is the length along which permeation of oxygen is occurring through the porous debond region. Assuming flow controlled debond growth, debond length (d) is set equal to length of porous flow regime (x_0), where “A” is the projected area of debond, and p is partial pressure of oxygen inside the debond. From Darcy’s law of flow in a porous medium, the rate of oxygen flow, u , into the debond region can be written, as given by Williams [14],

$$\frac{dx_0}{dt} = u = \frac{A}{c\eta} \left(\frac{dp}{dx} \right) \quad (2)$$

Where η is the viscosity and c is a constant. From equation (2), it can be shown that,,

$$d = \left(\frac{-2SAC_0}{c\eta} \right)^{1/2} \sqrt{t} \quad (3)$$

where “d” is the debond length. Details of this derivation are presented in Roy et.al. [15]. As evident from equation (3), for permeation controlled debond growth, debond length at the fiber/matrix interface due to oxidative degradation is directly proportional to the square-root of time.

Least-squares fit for debond length from experiments

A least-squares fit was employed to fit the experimental data for debond length due to diffusion complying with square-root of time as shown in Figure 4 for oxidation of a G30-500/PMR-15 unidirectional laminate in air at 288° C. From the least-square fit, the following relationship between debond length d , and time, t was established,

$$d(t) = B\sqrt{t} \quad (4)$$

where $B= 23.68$ for G30-500/PMR-15. A comparison of the functional form of equation (4) with equation (3) corroborates the use of Darcy’s law for predicting debond length due to permeation controlled debond growth at the micro-scale. Oxygen concentration boundary conditions along the length of the debond, in conjunction with the diffusion-reaction equation for the polymer matrix [9], and cohesive layer element at the fiber/matrix interface were incorporated in a in-house test-bed finite element code (NOVA-3D) to predict debond length as a function of time using a nonlinear finite element solution technique that takes into account the moving boundary at the debond tip. The material parameters used in the simulation are listed in Roy et.al. [15]. Figure 5 shows that the debond length history predicted by NOVA-3D compares well with the evolution of average debond length from experimental data for G30-500/PMR-15, despite some scatter in the test data at higher aging times. In Figure 6, debond growth rate computed from NOVA-3D is compared with least-squares fit of experimental data, again showing excellent agreement. As can be observed from this figure, after debond initiation at fiber/matrix interface near the laminate edge, the initial decrease in debond growth rate is very rapid. Subsequently, the debond growth rate asymptotically approaches a constant value after over 3000 hours of exposure.

ANISTROPIC DAMAGE MODELING FOR FIBER/MATRIX DEBONDING

Derivation of damage mechanics model

Based on the continuum damage mechanics (CDM) approach proposed by Talreja [7,8], Figure 7 shows a representative volume element (RVE) with full circumferential fiber/matrix debond of length d . We assume that the debond surfaces are symmetrical about three orthogonal planes, one of which splits a fiber longitudinally in two halves and the other is normal to the fiber axis. Assuming that the undamaged composite is transversely isotropic with the plane normal to the fiber axis as the plane of isotropy, we define the coordinate axes with X_1 axis parallel to fibers as shown in Figure 7. For an RVE where V_f is

Figure 5. Predicted debond length vs. time from FEA analysis (NOVA-3D).

Figure 6. Debond growth rate vs. time using FEA for 5% shrinkage

fiber volume fraction, R is the fiber radius, L_R is the length of RVE, $\mathbf{d}(t)$ is the fiber/matrix debond length in longitudinal direction at time t , and a is a damage influence parameter analogous to mode I crack-opening displacement, a symmetric damage tensor at the debond surface may be defined as [7],

$$d_{ij} = \frac{1}{V_{RVE}} \int_S a n_i n_j dS \quad (5)$$

It can be shown that the component of the damage in the X_3 -direction at time t is,

$$d_{33}(t) = \frac{1}{V_{RVE}} \left(2 \int_0^\pi a \sin^2 \theta \cdot d(t) \cdot R \cdot d\theta \right) = \frac{a V_f d(t)}{R L_R} \quad (6)$$

Details of the derivation can be found in Roy et al. [15]. In Equation (6), d_{33} represents the same damage entity for a full circumferentially debonded fiber. If the crack opening displacement a is assumed to be proportional to a characteristic crack dimension [7], i.e., $a = k\sqrt{S}$, where S is the surface area of the debond, and k is a proportionality constant, then the damage parameter can be written as,

$$\delta(t) = \frac{k V_f d(t) \sqrt{S(t)}}{R L_R} \quad (7)$$

Defining $S(t) = 2\pi R d(t)$ as the area of debond at time t , the damage parameter can be expressed as,

$$\delta(t) = k V_f \sqrt{2\pi \left(\frac{L_R}{R} \right)} \left(\frac{d(t)}{L_R} \right)^{3/2} \quad (8)$$

Figure 7. Representative volume element containing fiber/matrix debond.

Figure 8. Symmetric laminate damage model for three point bending test

Formulation of stiffness coefficient matrix for fiber/matrix debond

Thermo-mechanical response of a structure with internal damage can be described using fundamental principles of irreversible thermodynamics [16]. The internal variable for the debond damage configuration is $\delta(t)$ as given by equation (8), and the response function has following form,

$$\Phi = \Phi(\varepsilon_{ij}, \delta) \quad (9)$$

The elements of integrity basis for transversely isotropic symmetry [17], retaining up to second-order term in ε_{ij} and linear terms in δ , assuming $\delta \ll 1$, are,

$$\varepsilon_{11}, \varepsilon_{22} + \varepsilon_{33}, (\varepsilon_{22} - \varepsilon_{33})^2 + 4\varepsilon_{23}^2, \varepsilon_{12}^2 + \varepsilon_{13}^2, \delta, \delta(\varepsilon_{22} - \varepsilon_{33}), \delta\varepsilon_{23}, \delta\varepsilon_{12}\varepsilon_{13}, \delta(\varepsilon_{12}^2 - \varepsilon_{13}^2) \quad (10)$$

The polynomial expansion of the Helmholtz free energy function, Φ , in the absence of residual stresses, takes the following form [7],

$$\rho\Phi = \rho\Phi_0 + \rho\Phi_d \quad (11)$$

where, ρ is the density of the material, Φ_0 is a homogeneously quadratic function of strain (ε_{ij}) representing the undamaged state of the material, and Φ_d is a homogeneously quadratic function of strain and a linear function of the damage parameter δ , incorporating the influence of damage on material stiffness. Constructed using the irreducible integrity bases given in equation (10), Φ_d has the following form [7],

$$\rho\Phi_d = A_1\delta\varepsilon_{11}^2 + A_2\delta(\varepsilon_{22} + \varepsilon_{33})^2 + A_3\delta\varepsilon_{11}(\varepsilon_{22} + \varepsilon_{33}) + A_4\delta[(\varepsilon_{22} - \varepsilon_{33})^2 + 4\varepsilon_{23}^2] + A_5\delta(\varepsilon_{12}^2 + \varepsilon_{13}^2) + A_6\delta(\varepsilon_{12}^2 - \varepsilon_{13}^2) + A_7\delta\varepsilon_{12}\varepsilon_{13} + A_8\delta\varepsilon_{11}\varepsilon_{23} + A_9\delta\varepsilon_{23}(\varepsilon_{22} + \varepsilon_{33}) + A_{10}\delta\varepsilon_{11}(\varepsilon_{22} - \varepsilon_{33}) + A_{11}\delta(\varepsilon_{22}^2 - \varepsilon_{33}^2) \quad (12)$$

Where, A_1 through A_{11} are constant coefficients. The fourth-rank material stiffness tensor is given by the sum of the undamaged and damaged components,

$$C_{ijkl} = C_{ijkl}^0 + C_{ijkl}^d \quad (13)$$

$$\text{Where, } C_{ijkl}^0 = \rho \frac{\partial^2 \Phi_0}{\partial \varepsilon_{ij} \partial \varepsilon_{kl}} \quad \text{and} \quad C_{ijkl}^d = \rho \frac{\partial^2 \Phi_d}{\partial \varepsilon_{ij} \partial \varepsilon_{kl}} \quad (14)$$

Here, C^0 is the stiffness tensor for an undamaged orthotropic elastic material, and the tensor C^d represents the change in stiffness coefficients due to the presence of damage in the form of fiber/matrix debonding.

Degradation of Engineering Moduli

Linearization of equation (14) leads to expressions for the in-plane engineering moduli after thermo-oxidative debonding damage has taken place, given by [7],

$$\begin{aligned} E_1^*(t) &= E_1^0 + 2\delta(t)[\bar{A}_1 - \bar{A}_2\nu_{12}^0 + \bar{A}_3(\nu_{12}^0)^2] \\ E_2^*(t) &= E_2^0 + 2\delta(t)[\bar{A}_3 - \bar{A}_2\nu_{21}^0 + \bar{A}_1(\nu_{21}^0)^2] \\ \nu_{12}^*(t) &= \nu_{12}^0 + 2\delta(t)\frac{1 - \nu_{12}^0\nu_{21}^0}{E_2^0}\left[\frac{1}{2}\bar{A}_2 - \bar{A}_3\nu_{12}^0\right] \\ G_{12}^*(t) &= G_{12}^0 + 2\delta(t)\bar{A}_4/4 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where, E_1^0, E_2^0, ν_{12}^0 and G_{12}^0 are the in-plane elastic properties of the undamaged composite lamina, and $\bar{A}_1, \bar{A}_2, \bar{A}_3$ and \bar{A}_4 are constant coefficients from the continuum damage mechanics model. A numerical methodology for determining the unknown constant coefficients is presented in next section.

DAMAGE EVOLUTION MODEL FOR A COMPOSITE LAMINATE

Consider a unidirectional G30-500/PMR-15 laminate of thickness h , subjected to a load P at the mid-span as shown in Figure 8. In this case study, the unidirectional fibers are assumed to run parallel to the X-axis, and thermo-oxidative degradation of the laminate is assumed to occur primarily due to the progressive debonding of the fiber/matrix interface at the free edges of the laminate induced by shrinkage stresses in the matrix due to oxidation. Assume that the average extent of the zone of thermal-oxidative degradation from the laminate edge at time t is given by $d(t)$, as shown in Figure 8. For an orthotropic unidirectional symmetric laminate undergoing cylindrical bending, the moment curvature relationship reduces to,

$$D_{11}^* \frac{d^2 w^*}{dx^2} = M(x) \quad 0 < x < d(t) \quad (16)$$

Where, the bending stiffness after thermo-oxidative damage,

$$D_{11}^* = \frac{1}{12} b h^3 \left(\frac{E_1^*}{1 - \nu_{12}^* \nu_{21}^*} \right) \quad (17)$$

In equations (16) and (17), b is the width of the laminate, h is the thickness, and $M(x)$ is the applied bending moment. Superscript (*) denotes material properties that have undergone thermo-oxidative damage, as defined in equation (16). Assuming that the average length of the interfacial debond is $d(t)$ at time t , and using symmetry, the moment-curvature relationship for the undamaged laminate can be expressed as,

$$D_{11} \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} = M(x) \quad d(t) < x < L/2 \quad (18)$$

Where,

$$D_{11} = \frac{1}{12} b h^3 \left(\frac{E_1^0}{1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0} \right) \quad (19)$$

For three-point bending of a simply supported laminate as shown in Figure 8, the bending moment is,

$$M(x) = -\frac{P}{2} x \quad 0 < x < L/2 \quad (20)$$

An expression for the deflection at the mid-span of the thermo-oxidatively aged laminate can be obtained as given by,

$$w\left(\frac{L}{2}\right)_{aged} = \frac{PL^3}{48D_{11}} - \frac{Pd^3(t)}{6} \left(\frac{1}{D_{11}} - \frac{1}{D_{11}^*} \right) \quad (21)$$

If we rewrite equation (21) in the form,

$$w\left(\frac{L}{2}\right)_{aged} = \frac{PL^3}{48\bar{D}_{11}}$$

where, \bar{D}_{11} is the overall effective (damaged) laminate bending stiffness. Finally, the normalized effective bending stiffness for the aged laminate can be obtained, given by,

$$\frac{\bar{D}_{11}}{D_{11}} = \frac{PL^3}{48D_{11}w\left(\frac{L}{2}\right)_{aged}} \quad (22)$$

where, $w(L/2)$ is given by equation (21). Details of the derivation can be found in Roy et al. [15].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the laminate analysis results presented in this section, the evolution of the average fiber/matrix debond length, $d(t)$, as a function of time is obtained using equation (8). The corresponding damage parameter $\delta(t)$ for the laminate analysis is defined by setting the debond length equal to the micromechanical RVE length (i.e., $d(t)=L_R$) in equation (8), representing a fully debonded fiber/matrix interface of length $d(t)$ at time t , giving,

$$\delta(t) = kV_f \sqrt{2\pi \left(\frac{d(t)}{R}\right)} \quad (23)$$

The predicted variation of normalized bending stiffness (\bar{D}_{11}/D_{11}) with normalized fiber/matrix debond length for a unidirectional G30-500/PMR-15 laminate is shown in Figure 9 for different values of the damage opening proportionality constant \mathbf{k} (refer to equation (8)). Figure 10 depicts the predicted variation of normalized laminate bending stiffness (\bar{D}_{11}/D_{11}) with time, based on the NOVA-3D predictions of the debond growth rate shown in Figure 5. From these figures it is evident that, initially, the effect of debond growth on bending stiffness is not very significant until the debond length, $d(t)$, from each edge approaches $\sim 15\%$ of the laminate span. Subsequently, a dramatic reduction in the effective bending stiffness is predicted as the debond length increases with time. A parametric sensitivity study of the influence of the damage opening proportionality constant \mathbf{k} on effective bending stiffness as depicted in Figures 9 and 10 reveals that the effective bending stiffness is quite sensitive to the value of \mathbf{k} for the range of properties selected in the present analysis.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper a simple methodology is presented for transitioning from a micro-mechanics (RVE) based kinetic model to the macro-scale structural level, through the use of continuum damage mechanics (CDM). The strong anisotropy in the longitudinal direction observed in the thermal-oxidation of unidirectional composite lamina is accounted for in this model. Darcy's law is employed to model oxygen permeation in the porous region at the fiber/matrix interface to develop a shrinkage-induced permeation-controlled debond growth model. Debond initiation and growth is incorporated in the model through the use of a cohesive layer with a prescribed traction-separation law, and the damage parameters thus obtained are used to predict long-term behavior at the laminate level.

From the analytical predictions it is evident that, initially, the effect of debond growth on laminate bending stiffness is not very significant until the debond length, $d(t)$, from each

Figure 9. Variation of normalized bending stiffness \bar{D}_{11}/D_{11} with debond length for different values of the damage parameter k .

Figure 10. Variation of normalized bending stiffness \bar{D}_{11}/D_{11} with time for different values of the damage parameter k .

edge approaches ~15% of the laminate span. Subsequently, a dramatic reduction in the effective bending stiffness is predicted as the debond length increases with time.

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References

1. Colin, X., Verdu, J., *Composite Sci. and Tech.*, 65, 411-419, 2005.
2. Colin, X., Marais, C., Verdu, J., *Comp. Sci. and Tech.*, 65, 117-127, Jan. 2005.
3. Tandon, G.P., Pochiraju, K.V., and Schoeppner, G.A, *Poly. Degr. and Sta.*, **91**(8), 2006.
4. Pochiraju, K.V., Tandon, G.P., *J. of Eng. Materials Tech.*, Vol. 128, pp107-116, 2006.
5. Pochiraju, K.V., Tandon, G. P., Schoeppner, G.A., *Mech. of Time Dep. Materials*, 2007.
6. Wang, S. S., Chen, X., *Journal of Eng. Materials and Tech.* 128, 81-89, 2006.
7. Talreja, R., *Mech. of Material*, 12, 165-180, 1991.
8. Talreja, R., *J. of Material Science*, 41, 6800-6812, 2006.
9. Crank, J., *Mathematics of Diffusion*, 2nd Edition, Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1975.
10. Roy, S., Wang, Y., Park, S. and Liechti, K. M., *ASME J. of Eng. Material and Tech.*, Vol. 128, No. 1, pp 11-17, 2006.
11. Roy, S., Wang, Y., Park, S., Xu, D., and Liechti, K.M., *J. of Mechanics. of Advanced. Material and Structures*, 14:1-12, 2007.
12. Needleman, A., *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, 54, 525-531, 1987.
13. Wise, J., Gillen, K.T. Clough, R.L, *Polymer*, 38, 1929-1944 (1997).
14. Williams, J.G., *Fracture Mechanics of Polymers*, Ellis Horwood Limited, 1984.
15. Roy, S., Singh, S., and Schoeppner, G.A, *J. of Material Science*, 43, 6651-6660, 2008
16. Coleman, B.D. and Gurtin, M.E., *Journal of Chemical Physics*, 47, 597.
17. Smith , G. F., *Quarterly of Applied Mathematics* ,39, 509, 1982.